

TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH LITERARY DEVICES

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Abstract: Literature plays an important role in teaching four basic language skills like reading, writing, listening and speaking. However, when using literature in the language classroom, skills should never be taught in isolation but in an integrated way. Teachers should try to teach basic language skills as an integral part of oral and written language use, as part of the means for creating both referential and interactional meaning, not merely as an aspect of the oral and written production of words, phrases and sentences.

Key words: imaginative literature, reading, foreign language, integration

Аннотация: Литература играет важную роль в обучении четырех основных языковых навыков, таких как чтение, письмо, аудирование и речь. Однако при использовании литературы в языковой аудитории навыки никогда не должны преподаваться изолированно. Учителя должны стараться преподавать базовые языковые навыки как неотъемлемую часть устного и письменного языка, а также создавать интерактивный смысл.

Ключевые слова: художественная литература, иностранный язык, чтение, интеграция

Reading will never lose its relevance, as a kind of intellectual activity, as a means of spiritual and moral education and as a source of aesthetic pleasure. Therefore, the use of the grandiose possibilities of the book in the study of a foreign language is conditioned. In the classes on extracurricular reading, strengthening of

interdisciplinary ties takes place through acquaintance with classics and contemporary authors of the country of the studied language, with their works reflecting in some way the realities of the country's language and culture, opening a "window" to the world of another culture, process of intercultural communication.

Reasons for using literary texts in foreign language classes according to Collie and Slater, there are four main reasons which lead a language teacher to use literature in the classroom. The world of a novel, play, short story is an imaginary one, it presents a full and colorful setting in which characters from many social and regional backgrounds can be described.¹ A reader can discover the way, the characters in such literary works see the world outside, their feelings, customs, traditions, what they do, believe in, how they speak and behave in different places, parties. (Collie, J. and S.Slater)

Teachers are the basic pillars to teach through literature trying to attract them to this field. And we, as teachers are the ones who must make students get closer to Literature and make them feel it is not as abstract as they think. In translation courses, many language teachers make their students translate literary texts like short stories or poems into the native language. And by this way students get chance to practice their lexical, syntactic, semantic and stylistic knowledge.

The first reading can be done by the teacher and should not require students to perform a large and complex task. It is necessary that they enjoy reading, and too many tasks can deprive them of this. Let them get acquainted with the fragment and check their predictions, or answer a very general question about the text.

During the early stages of literature in foreign language teaching classical works by renowned authors were integrated into the curriculum. These texts were mostly used for translation purposes and exercises on reading comprehension. This led the students to look in a dictionary for each and every foreign word they come across. Literature in FLT tends to emphasize its role in improving communicative competence and create

¹ Stern, S. 2018. "An Integrated Approach to Literature in ESL / EFL" in Teaching English as a Second or Foreign Language. ed. Murcia, M. Boston: Heinle&Heinle Publishers.(2018 p330).

an awareness in students on the culture and society of the relevant country. The didactics of literature in foreign language teaching suggest different strategies to familiarize students with understanding and interpreting literary texts in a foreign language.

First of all, literary text is an excellent source of new vocabulary. The literary work is able to enrich the vocabulary of students and help to consolidate previously learned words and expressions in memory.

However, literary texts serve not only to illustrate the natural functioning of grammatical structures and lexical units, but also help to develop all 4 language skills: reading, listening, speaking and writing.

A warm-up can help students start thinking about a topic that will be affected in the selected piece of the work. Ideas for the task: a short discussion of the topic, a quiz on the topic.

The warm-up can focus on the source of the literary fragment. You can invite students to read a short reference about this. You can discuss or briefly tell them how this work is so famous. Reading fiction in English allows you to broaden the horizons of learners, learn about various cultural and historical events, increase active and passive vocabulary, multiply both linguistic and general cultural knowledge. Reading in English contributes to the dialogue of cultures, acquaints students with the realities inherent in another culture, other peoples and nationalities.

Methodology of research. The use of literary texts for reading in the teaching of English promotes the development of intellectual and cognitive abilities. Newly acquired linguistic and sociocultural knowledge and skills can significantly improve the level of motivation of students and help them feel more confident in using English — regardless of their level of language training.

Teaching of English is very closely connected with the study of English culture and literature. The familiarity with the best examples of classical and modern literature undoubtedly takes place in the culture of the countries of the studied language.

Fiction plays an important role in shaping the human personality. In fiction, the experience of many generations, basic moral and spiritual values are laid. Through reading, students absorb the norms of moral behavior and morality. During reading, both the cognitive and emotional spheres of the personality are involved.

Teachers indicate pronunciation errors of the students during the act of such activities so as to correct such errors.¹

General analysis. We noticed that Literature plays an important role in teaching four basic language skills like reading, writing, listening and speaking. However, when using literature in the language classroom, skills should never be taught in isolation but in an integrated way. Teachers should try to teach basic language skills as an integral part of oral and written language use, as part of the means for creating both referential and interactional meaning. In reading lesson, discussion begins at the literal level with direct questions of fact regarding characters, settings, etc.

When selecting a novel to be used in the foreign language class, the language teacher should pay attention to whether the novel has an intriguing story that will be of interest to the entire class. Themes and settings captivating their imagination and exploring the human condition should be included in the nature of the selected novels. Novel should have a powerful, fast-paced plot and interesting, well delineated, memorable characters. The content of the novel should be suitable to students' cognitive and emotional levels. The study of foreign language suggests broad spectrum of methods and forms of sign language in the foreign literature. Reading literary text, creative work, the student interprets an intensive lexicon, linguistic analysis of texts, compare it with his native language.

The ideal way for many to increase understanding of verbal and nonverbal aspects of communication in the country within which that language is spoken – a visit or an extended stay- is not probable and for such learners literature is useful. It provides learners with a wide range of individual lexical and syntactic items. They become

¹ Stern, S. 2018. "An Integrated Approach to Literature in ESL / EFL" in Teaching English as a Second or Foreign Language. ed. Murcia, M. Boston: Heinle&Heinle Publishers.(2018 p337).

familiar with many features of the written language and reading. They learn about functions of sentences, ways of connecting ideas and by this way they develop their writing skills. They become more productive. When the learner reads a literary text, he begins to inhabit it. He becomes a part of this text. Understanding the meaning of story he becomes enthusiastic to find out what happens event unfold via the climax.

Benefits of literature and what makes us to use literature in English language teaching:

1. Learners can learn the contextual meaning of famous phrases.
2. They can enhance their vocabulary.
3. They can improve not only their lexicological knowledge, but also the language that they use for specific purposes.
4. Learning English through Literature can provide learners to learn and discover their creativity, imagination.
5. Learners can live Literature, by reading and living it they can be impressed into a different person.
6. By reading English literature learners learn how Western culture has developed through various periods.
7. Reading literary texts learners can develop their independence and it becomes easy to use unfamiliar words.
8. Reading makes students feel themselves comfortable and free,
9. It helps students coming from various backgrounds communicate with each other because of its universal language,
10. Literature helps students to go beyond the surface meaning and dive into underlying meanings,
11. It acts as a perfect vehicle to help students understand the positions of themselves as well as the others by transferring these gained knowledge to their own world.

Maley lists some of the reasons for regarding literature as a potent resource in the language classroom as follows:¹

1. Universality
2. Non-triviality
3. Personal Relevance
4. Variety
5. Interest
6. Economy and Suggestive Power
7. Ambiguity

Choosing books relevant to the real-life experiences, emotions, or dreams of the learner is of great importance. Language difficulty has to be considered as well. If the language of the literary work is simple, this may facilitate the comprehensibility of the literary text but is not in itself the most crucial criterion. Interest, appeal, and relevance are also prominent. Enjoyment; a fresh insight into issues felt to be related to the heart of people's concerns; the pleasure of encountering one's own thoughts or situations exemplified clearly in a work of art; the other, equal pleasure of noticing those same thoughts, feelings, emotions, or situations presented by a completely new perspective: all these are motives helping learners to cope with the linguistic obstacles that might be considered too great in less involving material.

Literature helps students acquire a native-like competence in English, express their ideas in good English, learn the features of modern English, learn how the English linguistic system is used for communication, see how idiomatic expressions are used, speak clearly, precisely, and concisely, and become more proficient in English, as well as become creative, critical, and analytical learners.²

There are learners think that it is too difficult bored to learn a language by reading literal texts. But teachers' duty is to help them solve this problem. Because it gets

¹ Maley, A. 2015 "Down from the Pedestal: Literature as Resource" in *Literature and the Learner: Methodological Approaches*. Cambridge: Modern English Publications (2015 p 12)

² Clanfield.L. Teaching materials: using literature in the ESL/EFL classroom.

<http://www.onestopenglish.com/methodology/teaching-materials-using-literature-in-the-efl/esl-classroom>.
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learners closer to language, culture and customs. It helps them how to write and spell correctly.

Conclusion. Literature in all forms is everywhere in today's society and with this idea it is clear just how important it is. Literature is a central part of many lives. Studying language through Literature has the opportunity to find similarities in two different cultures. It helps learners enrich their vocabulary and start speaking language better. When reading Old English Literature students learn about history, customs and see how London looked through the eyes of Dickens when reading novels, poems, stories etc.

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